

Extra-Peritoneal Caesarean Section or Back to the Future? What are the Limits to its Spread?

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Abstract

Extra-peritoneal caesarean section is not a new technique, but was described more than two centuries ago. So why has it not been adopted and what are the limits to its dissemination despite its reported advantages, we are going to describe the so-called French extra-peritoneal caesarean section technique and see what its advantages and disadvantages are.

Introduction

Caesarean section is the most practical intervention in the world. Auguste Baudelocque first described the extra-peritoneal caesarean section in 1823. In 1909, Latzko [1] described the lateral route and Waters [2] in 1940, the supra-vesical route. The technique was most widely used in the United States between 1930 and 1950.

Extra-peritoneal caesarean section was gradually abandoned with the advent of antibiotics.

Patient and observation

Surgical technique

We describe the modified extra peritoneal caesarean section technique described in 1996 by Denis Fauck and Jacques Henri Ravina: the Fauck 'French Ambulatory Caesarean Section' [3].

Incision 2 cm above the pubic symphysis (Figure 1), horizontal aponeurotic buttonhole over 2 cm (Figure 2) then left paramedian vertical incision over 14 cm

(Figure 3), then the rectus femoris muscle is reclined to the left (Figure 4), the left intervesico uterine canal is opened (Figure 5) and the bladder is reclined to the right thus freeing the inferior segment to allow a segmental hysterotomy (Figure 6).

Figure 1: Incision 2 cm above the Pubic Symphysis

More Information

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Figure 2: Horizontal Fascial Buttonhole over 2 cm

Figure 3: 14 cm Left Paramedian Vertical Incision

Figure 4: The Right Rectus Muscle is Reclined to the Left

Figure 5: The Left Intervesico Uterine Canal is Opened

Discussion

The extra-peritoneal caesarean section seems to have many advantages, particularly in terms of pain during and after the operation, which means that the dose of anaesthetic can be reduced, there is no paralytic ileus, which means that the baby can be fed quickly (3 hours later) and the stay can be outpatient.

in addition, the fact that the peritoneal cavity is not opened eliminates the risk of infection and adhesions. However, the limited scope of the operation means that this technique cannot be used in all situations, particularly in emergencies, placenta previa, fetal macrosomia and transverse presentation, where the supravescical route must be used. It should be noted that for some authors, repeated caesarean section is a contraindication, but not for others, including Durfee [4].

Figure 6: Segmental Hysterotomy

What are the limits to the spread of this technique?

- The simplification of caesarean section techniques, whether in terms of laparotomy, hysterography or peritonisation, and the need for a greater learning curve for the extra-peritoneal route mean that this technique is being abandoned.
- The frequent need for instrumental extraction due to the restricted approach, which can hamper foetal extraction [5]. There are three types of risk associated with this technique: bladder injuries, which are reported in 0 to 7% of cases [6] [7]. Peritoneal openings 4 to 39%.

The difficulties of fetal extraction with recourse to instrumental extractions

The technique of extra peritoneal caesarean section seems safe and attractive despite the rate of instrumental extraction, and should be more widely used [8].

At the very least, it should be preferred in cases of premature rupture of membranes lasting more than 24 hours, death in utero or chorioamnionitis.

The aim is to avoid dissemination of infected products of endo-uterine origin into the peritoneal cavity it avoids opening the peritoneal cavity (the peritoneum is not opened, the bladder is pushed back to the left so as to approach the SI without opening the peritoneum).

Conclusion

Extra-peritoneal caesarean section appears to be the most anatomical route, reducing the risk of infection and adhesions. However, the difficulty of learning to use it limits its spread. It should be the preferred route for scheduled caesarean sections, which will increase

the learning curve and familiarise the teams with its practice.

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Authors' Contributions

Lounas BENGHANEM: data collection, bibliographic research and writing of the article.

Bouزيد ADDAD: proofreading and supervision of the writing of the article.

Lydia FAÏD: proofreading and supervision of the writing of the article.

Kamel HAÏL: proofreading and supervision of the writing of the article.

Radia BENYAHIA: proofreading and supervision of the writing of the article.

Chahira MAZOUZI: proofreading and supervision of the writing of the article.

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